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SMART DISPATCHER: AN ANDROID DOCUMENT TRACKING SYSTEM

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ABSTRACT

Documents, generally, has been identified as an important element in decision making as well as customer service relations. Motivated by the need to secure these documents from loss or theft while providing easy access to them, several technologies have been proposed by previous authors to track of these documents as they move from one office to another. Some of the proposed solutions include: barcodes, radio frequency identification (RFID) and augmented reality. While most of these works have been either web-based or desktop, none have been developed as a mobile application to allow users work on both paper and electronic documents remotely. In this paper, we designed and developed an android hybrid application for tracking of both paper and electronic documents. Notifications on the current status of the document are forwarded in form of both SMS and email. Our proposed system is designed using Object Oriented Methodology; and was implemented with Java, XML, PHP and MySQL. After evaluation with existing document management systems, our proposed system proved to allow for users track and work on documents remotely; and capable of providing real-time updates on the documents' current location.

Keywords: Document tracking, electronic documents, paper documents, object oriented methodology

1. INTRODUCTION

Document Tracking System (DTS) (also called File Tracking System (FTS) or File Tracking and Monitoring System (FTMS)) is a web-based application that manages all the files movement at any time from one desk/room to another one. It may include generation of receipts and files, updating its status, opening of new files, tracking the movement of files, dispatching letters/files, recording their track, etc. Any desk/room can receive and send request and decisions at any time. The system follows a procedure of file unique numbering and enables file management, file status monitoring, file movement tracking, etc (Krasniqi, 2013; Banday, Sheikh & Rather, 2015).

Generally, documents are major sources of communication in most cooperate organizations. These documents in most cases have to move from one office to another until it gets to the

intended recipient. While in transit, there could be security challenges arising from theft, misplacement or loss due to poor documentation. These situations have often led to huge financial loss, man-hour-loss or even malicious disclosure of sensitive information. Against this backdrop, several techniques and technologies have been deployed in recent times to track both paper and electronic documents. These include the use of dispatch registers (Banday et al, 2015); web based applications (Edem & Onwuachu, 2014); barcode systems (Perocho, 2012); radio frequency identification (RFID) systems (Rahman, 2018; Ishayk, Othman, Talib & Ilyas 2017); augmented reality systems (Sallam, 2016) and so on. While some of these systems have been devoted to electronic office (paperless) environment allowing users to store and monitor changes to electronic documents with no consideration to paper documents, others are purely intended for papers documents for tracking their movements between various

offices in an organization. Yet these two types of documents (paper and electronic) have continued to co-exist for cooperative operations. Even with the proliferation of Internet connectivity and its abundant digital contents, the continual use of papers, have been attributed to the level of process and volume of work involved; the cost and convenience attached to using it; and other cooperative preferences (Sallam, 2016; Banday et al, 2015). Hence, in order to accommodate these contemporary use of both papers and electronic documents in cooperative settings viz-a-viz their security, monitoring and easy access, there is need to for a system that captures both the storing and monitoring of changes to electronic documents; and the tracking of paper documents between offices easily - from remote locations.

This paper aims at designing and developing an android document tracking system that captures both the storing and monitoring of changes to electronic documents; and the tracking of paper documents between offices easily from remote locations. Our system's performance will be measured on its ability to: create and monitor changes to electronic documents; to dispatch and track movements of paper documents; provide notifications in both SMS and email on current status and location of documents; and allow users to work on electronic documents from remote locations.

2. RELATED WORK

Perocho (2012) designed a document management system for a medical centre using waterfall model. This automated system used barcode technology. Like every barcode project, this system was susceptible to physical damage and scan error; in addition, Perocho's system was expensive for small and medium enterprise to implement. Similarly, Rahman (2018) demonstrated how radio frequency identification (RFID) technology could be integrated with a computer application to track paper documents. Rahman's tracking system could automatically track the location and status of patient's medical files on real time. This real-time tracking of patient's file was made possible with the aid of RFID tags attached to the file; and the RFID scanner placed in each units of the hospital. Using the same Near Field Communication (NFC) technology (RFID tags), Ishayk, Othman, Talib and Ilyas (2017) developed a tracking system known as SPATRASE. With SPATRASE, the tracking was run as a mobile

application; and was used for tracking of students' paper work in the university. As an enhancement, SPARTRASE could store tracking information in Google Doc; thereby giving room for remote tracking using the client mobile application. However, the system did not provide a user interface to rename paper work details; and so, users were forced to use the pre-defined information stored in the tags to identify their documents.

Beyond tracking of paper documents, Prinz and Javeel (2004) developed a virtual desktop application for tracking the specific location of paper documents on an office desk; as well as linking these paper documents on the desk with their electronic version. This was done using unique labels printed on the paper documents, digital cameras and augmented reality. The printed labels provided the unique identification for each paper on the desk. The cameras took different pictures of the document on the desk; and using augmented reality, the system could simulate what the resultant pictures to identify and represent the location digitally. Whatever the user does to the paper (printed) document will be mirrored to the electronic copy. These include annotations and change of paper locations. Their system also uses WLAN, bluetooth and RFID setup. In addition, this virtual desktop was also run on PDAs and mobile devices to enable more cooperative processes and sharing of documents. Prinz et al system was tested using eight (8) RFID readers and twenty (20) tagged objects. Though this system proved more useful to remember folder that were covered under a pile of other documents; but, it was equally found to be less useful for finding documents. Sallam (2016) developed a similar system known PaperSpace. PaperSpace could link paper and digital documents; and as well simulate the location and organization of paper documents. However, it suffered the challenges of inability to detect paper which is pulled out of the pile; its inability to detect the removal of a pile; and delays in processing each frames (Sallam, 2016). Nguyen (2014) evaluated and implemented a cloud-based supply chain management (SCM) system for tracking and tracing the safety and on-time arrival of shipments. Electronic document interface (EDI) and enterprise resource planning (ERP) were interconnected to achieve this. Nguyen presented a SCM system that could support global deliveries instead of a single transportation like FedEx or DHL. Nguyen's system implemented several tracking

technologies which include forwarder tracking, automatic identification system (AIS) tracking, amazon web services (AWS) tracking, and global positioning system (GPS) tracking to track the shipments on the go and at different stations. Using Nguyen SCM system, tracking details were uploaded to the cloud to enable users and managers obtain the location and the status of shipments.

Edem and Onwuachu (2014) developed a document monitoring system and implemented it in Java and Microsoft SQL server. Their paper argued that the complexity of generating barcodes for document tracking has made it difficult for users and thus resulted to its low acceptance. Hence, the need for a graphic user interfaces (GUI) that is easy to use for both novice and experts. Their web-based system tracks documents by simply clicking a button in the system. However, this system is proprietary in nature; platform dependent; and did not have mobile version. University of Wincosin (2011) also, developed a web-based routing and tracking system called WISPER. As a web-based system, WISPER was specifically designed for tracking documents in the university community. Apart from tracking, WISPER allows for routing, approval, and negotiations of applications and agreements. The paper neither discussed the method of design nor the implementation tools used.

Omogbe, Azeta, Adewumi & Edeh (2014) and Kransniqi (2013) designed a file tracking system (FTS) for tertiary institutions. Their design was made to be web-based using object oriented analysis and designed (OOAD). Omogbe et al (2014) compared their proposed system with existing systems like information and data exchange advanced system (IDEAS), centralized file movement and tracking information system (CeFMaTIS) and infotronic systems. Both Omogbe et al (2014) and Kransniqi (2013) systems were adjudged to track both physical and electronic documents, platform independent, inexpensive to implement and could send notifications. However, both systems can only run on desktop system and were not used for arranging files even though they could search files. Also, while a Kransniqi (2013) system was designed to use RFID to track its paper documents, Omogbe et al (2014) did not provide how their system tracked paper documents.

From our review, we can deduce that most of the existing solutions were devoted to electronic

office (paperless) environment allowing users to store and monitor changes to electronic documents with no consideration to paper documents, others were purely intended for paper documents for tracking their movements between various offices in an organization; and none was devoted to handle the duo – paper and digital documents. Yet these two types of documents have continued to co-exist in cooperate environments. Again, the notifications provided by these systems were mostly in emails forcing the stakeholders to connect to the Internet whenever they chose to monitor their documents. Hence, there is need to for a system that captures both the storing and monitoring of changes to electronic documents; and as well, the tracking of paper documents between offices easily; and from remote locations.

3. SYSTEM DESIGN

To achieve our intended design for a mobile application, we used Universal Modelling Language (UML) to model the tracking of paper and electronic document for an academic institution. UML is the commonest tool used for object oriented analysis and design methodology. The following UML diagrams were employed in our design: use case diagrams, activity diagram and entity-relationship (ER) diagram.

3.1 Use Case Diagram

For the design of the proposed system, we identified two primary actors (the user and the administrator) and a secondary actor (the owner) (see Fig. 1). The document owner is expected to receive SMS and email notifications upon change of document's location and status; while other actors are expected to login into the system to interact with the system and log out when they are through with the system. The user of the system can either act as a document sender or a recipient depending on the state of the document. The user can create an electronic document; review an electronic documents; register a paper document; dispatch a document to another user (the recipient); and track the location and status of a document. Notifications are sent as both SMS and e-mail alerts. The system administrator manages both users and department.

Fig.1: Use case diagram of our proposed system

Fig.2: Activity diagram of document management

3.2 Activity Diagram

As illustrated in Fig. 2, a registered user logs in successfully after his credentials have been authenticated. The user proceeds to either work with existing document or create a new document depending on the task at hand. When the user chooses to work with existing documents, he can either track the movement history of the document or dispatch an existing document to another user. Upon dispatch, the detail of the document's new location is saved while notifications are sent to the owner and the receiver of the document.

in both SMS and email. Within Smart Tracker, the system user is assumed to be a staff of the organization who is expected to log into the system using his name and password in order to interact with the system. This user can: register new documents; dispatch existing documents to another user; and view the current location and status of the document. The document owner could either be a staff of the organization or any external person who does not have login access to the system. This document owner receives update on real-time condition and location of the document.

4. SYSTEM IMPLEMENTATION

Fig.2: High level model of the proposed System

Our proposed system, Smart Tracker, is built for Android platform. Smart Tracker consists of four main software modules namely: the document manager to enable the user access the system and manage his/her document, the document tracker to store the history of the document for every change of status and location, the notification generator to provide notifications to the document owner and the document recipient, and the database for storing document information and user activity. The document manager is hosted on the user's device as the front-end application; while the remaining are hosted at the cloud as back-end application. The document manager is implemented using Java and XML. MySQL server was used for the database while PHP was used to implement the document tracker and notification generator. Notifications are sent

4.1 Implementation Tools

Since our proposed system is intended to be platform independent and mobile based, we chose some development tools that will make this idea implementable. These tools include:

- Java is a full object-oriented programming language and the most common programming language for developing mobile applications. It is supported by most mobile devices and web browsers.
- XML is an enterprise standard for exchanging data on the Internet. It also used for designing the user interface of mobile applications. XML is supported by most browsers.

- PHP is an open source programming language used for handling back-end processing. It is supported by Apache, the most popular web server.
- MySQL is an open source database management software for housing of database in the web server. MySQL is supported by both Apache and PHP.

4.2 System Requirements

The proposed system, which operates in a client-server mode, requires both hardware and software to run. The hardware requirement for this system can either be a personal computer or an android device. For the personal computer:

1. An Ethernet port or an external MODEM;
2. RAM size: 512MB or above
3. Disk size: 20MB or above
4. Processor speed: 1GHZ or above

For the android device: The hardware requirement in which the new system will operate and function is an android phone. These android phones include the following: Tecno Y3, Y6, Gionee P3, P5w, ITEL 1701 etc.

The software requirement for this system is window XP or higher version for the personal computer and android 4.0 or higher for the android device.

5. EVALUATION

Our proposed document tracking system was tested using Android Emulator and ITEL P12 device (See APPENDIX1). After evaluation with existing document tracking systems, it was shown that Smart Tracker provides collaboration, tracking, and managing files; in addition to being less expensive to implement, user mobility; and its ability to forward notification in both pull and push mode. However, our proposed system can neither link printed paper documents with their counterpart electronic copies nor help users in organizing their documents as is obtainable with content and virtual desktop systems like PaperSpace (Table 1).

Table 1: Summary of our system evaluation and comparison with existing systems

Tracking System	Smart Tracker	Web FTS	PaperSpace	SPATRASE
Quality				
Collaboration/workflow	√	√	X	X
Tracking	√	√	√	√
File management	√	√	X	X
Mobility	√	X	X	X
Cost	Less	Less	High	High
Linking physical and electronic documents	X	X	√	X
Search capability	√	√	√	√
Organization of documents	X	X	√	x
Notification mode	Pull & Push	Pull	Pull	Pull

6. CONCLUSION

In this work, we reviewed the need to track both physical documents and digital documents remotely since the duo are the modus operandi for most cooperate entities. Furthermore, we also reviewed existing document tracking systems to buttress their strengths and weaknesses. Finally, we also proposed, designed and developed a mobile application to effectively track documents irrespective of type. In future, our system could be enhanced to accommodate the use of digital signatures to enforce better file security and encryption; to allow organizations to run it as an Intranet-cloud application using WIFI thereby eliminating the extra cost arising from Internet charges.

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APPENDIX 1: SCREENSHOTS OF THE PROPOSED SYSTEM

Smart Tracker

✕

Login Register

ss102

...

Login

[Lost your password ?](#)

Smart Tracker

Welcome :
okoro, Fedelis (ss102)
Registrar Department

Create File

Dispatch File

Track File

